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ANNUAL REPORT
OF THE ~~X~~
ARCHÆOLOGICAL DEPARTMENT
GWALIOR STATE
FOR
SAMVAT 1987, YEAR 1930-31.

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ANNUAL ADMINISTRATION REPORT
OF THE
DEPARTMENT OF ARCHÆOLOGY, GWALIOR STATE
FOR THE
YEAR ENDING 30th JUNE 1931, SAMVAT 1987.

PART I

I. Office Notes.

Charge.—M. B. Garde, Esq., the Superintendent, remained in charge of the Department till the 31st May 1931, when he was obliged to proceed on leave due to his sudden and serious illness. During his absence the charge of the current duties of the post remained with the undersigned.

2. *Leave.*—The Superintendent availed himself of one month's privilege leave from the 1st to the 30th June 1931.

Members of the subordinate staff enjoyed leave as follows :—

- (a) General Assistant : Privilege leave for 33 days at different times in the year.
- (b) Photographer-Draughtsman : 30 days' privilege leave from the 1st to the 30th June 1931.
- (c) Assistant Photographer-Draughtsman : 32 days' privilege leave at different times in the year.
- (d) Curator : Privilege leave for 40 days from the 6th October 1930 to the 15th November 1930.
- (e) Officer Accounts : Privilege leave for 31 days at different times in the year.
- (f) Officer Correspondence : Privilege leave for 40 days at different times in the year.
- (g) Record-keeper : Privilege leave for 11 days at different times and sick leave for one month and 28 days from the 13th August to the 14th October 1930.

3. *General.*—All members of the office staff discharged their respective duties harmoniously, diligently and carefully, for which I am glad to record my appreciation.

II. Administrative Changes and Orders.

4. No Circulars with special reference to the Department were issued during the year under report, except a notification for the guidance of the Archæological Department in the *Gwalior Government Gazette*, dated the 9th May 1931, under section 16 of the Act for the Protection of Ancient Monuments and Antiquities in the Gwalior State. The announcement directs that in case an antiquity is to be acquired in terms of the above quoted section of the Act and if the owner instead of accepting price for the same, desires to present the antiquity, it may be accepted and exhibited in the Archæological Museum with a label bearing name and aim of the donor.

III. Work at Headquarters.

5. In addition to the ordinary office routine work the following was done during the headquarters season :—

- (a) Annual Administration Report for the year 1929-30, Samvat 1986 was drawn up and submitted.
- (b) An album of important photographs taken during Samvat 1986 was prepared and submitted.
- (c) A chart containing a map of the Gwalior State showing important places of archæological interest in the State and illustrated with a photograph of one of the leading monuments from each place was prepared and presented to His Highness the Maharaja on the auspicious occasion of his Birthday.
- (d) Another chart similar to the above was prepared and supplied to the Home Member Sahib for reference.
- (e) New acquisitions of antiquities in the Museum were classified, arranged and labelled.
- (f) The coins received as treasure-trove finds or offered for sale and in exchange by institutions and private bodies were examined and disposed of.
- (g) Photographs of important archæological monuments which were exhibited in the Dak Bungalows of the State, were further supplemented this year with printed and framed notices giving a brief description of monuments, their situation and route.
- (h) Information called for from Revenue Officers in Districts for the *Directory of Forts* was compiled in the form of a table.
- (i) The compilation of statistical information regarding the work done by the Archæological Department during the first decade of its existence was proceeded with.
- (j) The preparation of albums of photographs of select Archæological Monuments for the information of visitors was taken in hand during the year of report.
- (k) Five special albums were prepared under the direction of the Department for presentation by the Darbar to Lord Hardinge, Lord Dufferin and their party at the time of their visit to Gwalior.
- (l) A set of 12 printed picture post-cards containing views of Chanderi monuments was brought out.
- (m) Short lectures on archæological topics illustrated by lantern slides were delivered at the request of various *Mandals* and *Samajas* during the *Ganesh Utsava*.

IV. Tours.

6. During the year under report the Superintendent spent 65 days in camp for the annual inspection of monuments already conserved, for directing the conservation works in progress and for listing monuments and for attending Conferences.

7. The Offg. Superintendent also toured for 14 days for directing and supervising the works of conservation in progress. The detailed tour diary is set forth in Appendix A.

8. The places visited by the Superintendent were :—
Bagh, Ujjain, Surwaya, Antri, Pawaya, Sesai, Padhavli, Bharoli, Paroli, Kherhat, Kulwar, Chanderi, Naderi, Mungaoli, Budhi Chanderi, Thoban, Mandasor, Narwar and Panchamnagar.
9. He also went to Palpur near Pohri to see the Home Member Sahib on tour and to Patna to attend the 6th session of the All-India Oriental Conference and the 12th session of the Indian Historical Records Commission.
10. The Offg. Superintendent visited the following places :—
Chanderi, Bhilsa, Ujjain, Mandasor and Bagh.

V. Conservation.

11. The work of conservation of ancient monuments was carried out during the year of report at Kherhat (Dist. Bhind), Padhavli (Dist. Tonwarghar), Lashkar (Dist. Gird), Chanderi (Dist. Esagarh), Badoh and Bhilsa (Dist. Bhilsa), Sondni (Dist. Mandasor), and Bagh (Dist. Amjhera).

12. Out of a number of non-recurring grants applied for for major repairs to certain monuments, only that for the conservation of the Bagh Caves was sanctioned. Out of the amount of Rs. 25,000 thus sanctioned for this work, a major portion was withheld later on and Rs. 8,000 only were allowed to be spent in the year of report. The small recurring grant provided for conservation in the regular budget was spent on necessary repairs to other monuments.

13. The list of monuments conserved and the amounts spent on their conservation are shown in Appendix B, while the important items of repairs carried out at different monuments are given below :—

14. *Kherhat*.—It is a small village 5 miles from Ater which in turn is 17 miles by *pucca* road to the north-west of Bhind. About a mile and a half to the south-east of the village, reached by a circuitous and zigzag path, in the midst of ravines lie the ruins of some Hindu temples of the 10th century, chiefly built of bricks, stone being used for door-frames, pillars and idols of worship. All except one of these temples have met with total destruction. A modern temple has been constructed on the site of another with material taken from the ruins. This modern temple and the only surviving old temple are locally known as *Sherbade-ki-mata* and *Mergade-ki-mata* respectively. These names, however, have no significant meaning.

15. The old brick temple (*Mergade-ki-mata*) was conserved in the year of report. It is an important monument being perhaps the only mediaeval brick temple in the Gwalior State. The exterior of this temple is decorated with moulded brick work. Such old brick temples are rare not only in the Gwalior State but also in other parts of India.

16. The chief items of conservation executed are :—

(a) The temple and its platform were freed from the jungle and debris with which they had been covered for centuries.

(b) The original platform was found to have been too much disturbed and decayed to be restored. It was, therefore, covered up with an earthen platform the edges of which were finished in slopes.

(c) The stone door-frame which had fallen off was found buried in the adjoining ravine below. It was taken out and reset in position.

(d) The floor of the interior of the temple was repaired. The damaged pedestal was rebuilt and the idol reinstated.

(e) The top of the *sikhara* which had been damaged, was made water-proof against rain with a layer of strong cement concrete. The roof of the shrine below the hollow of the *sikhara* was similarly treated with a coat of cement concrete.

(f) The temple is beset with ravines on its three sides. The available ground round the temple platform was levelled and demarcated with boundary pillars.

(g) Some fine sculptures which lay buried in the ruins of adjoining temples were unearthed, cleaned and arranged into a sort of open-air museum round the platform of the conserved temple.

17. *Padhavli*.—The monument repaired here is the remnant of a fine temple of the 10th century A.D. The work of conserving this monument was started in V.S. 1982 (for description of the monument see that year's A.R. p.6) and finally completed during the year under notice.

18. The items carried out during this year are :—

(a) The exposed top of the temple-roof was made water-tight by filling the gaps with cement concrete and the joints with coloured country *masala*.

(b) Some of the panels over the architraves which are decorated with fine sculptures depicting scenes from the epics were damaged by rain-water flowing over them. This water was diverted by providing projecting eaves round the open ceiling on the top.

(c) The floor of the porch was repaired.

(d) A printed descriptive notice in Hindi and English was put up in the porch.

(e) All later accretions were dismantled and the ground around was excavated for exposing the plinth of the temple, and the debris was thrown away beyond the temple limits.

(f) The original floor of the main platform of the temple was exposed but was found to be too uneven and expensive to be repaired. It was, therefore, covered up with a layer of fine earth and spread over with sand to give a neat appearance and proper surface for drainage.

(g) The site was cleared and tidied up and proper drainage was provided.

(h) As the original ground level of the temple is some feet below the present surrounding ground, made up of debris, retaining walls of rubble masonry were built on the west and south to hold up the banks and the sculptures and carvings found in the debris were arranged against these walls.

(i) The path from the lowest entrance of the *garhi* to the main gate ushering into the temple compound was cleared and the gate was barred with an iron pipe in order to prevent the access of cattle.

19. *Gwalior*.—The building Gujari Mahal which is situated inside the Gwalior Fort and is now being used for housing the Archæological Museum was fitted with water pipes at considerable cost in order to remove the long-felt want of good water supply for drinking purposes as also for the maintenance of a pot garden.

20. *Lashkar*.—The monument attended to here is the Chhatri of the late Maharani Lakshmi Bai of Jhansi, which was conserved three years back (vide *Annual Report* for V. S. 1985). This monument being situated on the station road—the leading thoroughfare of the capital town—attracts a large number

of visitors. In order to make this monument more inviting, the available area within the enclosure of the monument was converted into a modest park, in the year of report. Water pipe was provided both for the maintenance of the park as well as for drinking purposes. Further, the premises were fitted with electric lights on two lamp-posts which the municipal authorities have kindly undertaken to light free of charge.

21. *Chanderi*.—On the Chanderi Fort, near the ruins of the Naukhanda Mahal, there is a small tank traditionally known as *Johar Tal*. The tank is at present like a natural depression devoid of water and may be probably a big quarry pit from which stone was taken out for building the Naukhanda Mahal.

22. It is recorded in history that during the siege of this fort by Emperor Babar, many Rajput ladies performed the grim ceremony of *Johar* or self-immolation on the 29th January 1528 A. D., before the Rajput army under Medini Rai the then Raja of Chanderi issued out for their last desperate battle with the Emperor's army. Tradition has it that this *Johar* took place on the banks of this tank.

23. At the instance of the Home Member Sahib the Archæological Department proposed to commemorate this event by the construction of a suitable monument. It was intended in the first place to build a stone platform and to set upon it a sculpture and an inscription indicative of the event. It was further proposed that, if funds permitted, a *chhatri* or canopy should be erected over the sculpture and inscription on the platform. The proposal having been approved, the first part of the scheme was carried out in the year of report. It consists of a lower platform 12' x 12' x 3' with staircases in the northern and southern sides facing the road and the tank respectively. The lower platform carries on it a smaller one 6' x 6' x 2' 6" which is ultimately to be surmounted with the stone bearing a sculpture and inscription. The proposed *chhatri* will be built next year.

24. *Badoh*.—This decaying village (better known to archæologists by the name Baro Pathari) abounds in mediæval ruins. The following minor works were executed during the year in order to make up the deficiencies at the monuments which have been conserved already :—

(a) A descriptive notice printed and framed was set up at the Gadarmal temple which is the most prominent monument of the place.

(b) Short descriptive notices engraved on stones were set up near other monuments of importance.

(c) Two big stone figures of lions which had been picked up from the debris of the Gadarmal temple and set up on the platform at the time of conservation had been dislodged owing to the sinking of the floor under their weight. They were reset firmly after the floor had been restored.

(d) Similarly in the group of ruins known as Dasavatar temples, a huge broken sculpture of Varaha picked up from the debris had been set up in dry rubble masonry. But the parts got disjointed almost every year. To avoid repetition of this trouble the sculpture was secured with steel clamps and supported on the back with a *pucca* masonry wall.

25. *Bhilsa*.—There is an open-air collection of sculptures and architectural pieces at the Dak Bungalow. When some more sculptures were added to this collection, the wooden railing supporting and protecting sculptures gave way. It was, therefore, repaired and strengthened with extra intermediate supports of stone to withstand the thrust of some of the heavy

sculptures which rest against it. In so doing some of the sculptures had to be removed for inserting new supports. Hence the whole collection was re-arranged.

26. The surroundings of the Khamb Baba were further tidied up by dressing up the piece of ground at the end of the approach road and by replacing the clumsy *kachcha chabutra* of the neighbouring *nim* tree with a neat platform of *pucca* masonry.

27. Nearly all the monuments near Bhilsa except the caves at Udaygiri have now been connected with metalled roads. An approach road to the caves also is under contemplation. But as the construction of the road would take some time, the existing cart-track was specially repaired this year so as to facilitate the running of spring-vehicles during the fair-weather.

28. *Sondni*.—This small hamlet in the vicinity of Mandasor (ancient Dasapura) is known for the famous inscribed pillars of king Yasodharman of the 6th century A. D. The columns which lay half buried in the fields were picked up and exhibited on a masonry platform near the original site in V. S. 1979. The following special work was done here in the year of report :—

(a) The coping of the platform which was originally of thin slabs of Neemuch lime-stone having proved too weak was replaced with thicker and stronger slabs of Dhorra sand-stone. The Neemuch slabs taken off from here were used as uprights for encasing the plinth of the platform.

(b) The surrounding ground round the platform was overgrown with patches of *Kans* grass and had become unsightly. It was, therefore, dug up and freed from grass.

(c) Some of the fencing posts which had been shaken by cattle were reset securely and wiring was tightened. The heaps of debris near the fence from which cattle lept into the compound were removed.

(d) An approach road connecting the monument with the Mhow-Neemuch trunk road has been recently sanctioned but as its construction is bound to take some time the present cart-track was repaired so as to be of use to motorists during the fair-weather.

(e) The sign-board at the junction was overhauled and repaired.

29. *Khilchipura*.—It is a small village about two miles north of Mandasor. It was one of the suburbs of the ancient town of Dasapura. Here stood a surviving door-jamb of a Torana gateway of an ancient temple of about the 6th century A. D., the basement of which was exposed during the excavations carried out at the site (vide *A. R.* for V. S. 1979). The pillar came to be called *Sravan-ki-Kavad* from a fanciful interpretation of one of the sculptured panels on it. As the pillar is of considerable artistic and archaeological interest and as it stood in an out of the way place, it was removed and set up in the Mandasor Fort with the double purpose of ensuring its safety and of making it easily accessible to visitors.

30. As it was thought advisable to commemorate the original site of the pillar, an inscribed stone tablet fixed up in a masonry block was put up here in the year of report.

31. *Bagh*.—The place is chiefly known for its famous Buddhist caves and fresco paintings, all belonging to the 5th-7th centuries A.D. It will appear from the *Annual Reports* for the preceding years that an earnest attempt is being made for rescuing these valuable relics. As stated in the beginning, the

Council of Regency sanctioned during the year of report Rs. 25,000 for these caves but was obliged later on to withhold a major portion of the grant.

32. Of all the caves here, cave No. 4 is the most important and at the same time is in a sad condition of decay. Hence it claims urgent attention. Though considerable repair work has already been done in this cave, much is still left to be done. Consequently the grant made available in the year of report was used mainly in carrying out the most needful repairs to this cave.

33. Some of the important items of conservation of the caves are noted below :—

(a) Out of the many columns which support the big hall of cave No. 4 three were repaired by cutting decayed portions and inserting new cut-stone masonry in their place. Five new pillars were built in place of those which had fallen away altogether. The only surviving inner porch decorated with a beautiful frieze being disintegrated with cracks was in imminent danger of coming down. It was, therefore, supported completely by a frame-work of heavy steel girders and the cracking pillars supporting the frieze were bound up with strong iron bands. Important portions of decaying walls of the cave were repaired by underpinning the same with cut-stone masonry in cement.

(b) Cave No. 5 has an inner passage connecting it with the adjoining cave No. 6. The latter cave has collapsed badly and is too dangerous to be entered. It also shelters panthers. In order to prevent visitors from entering cave No. 6 and also to protect cave No. 5 against panthers or other wild animals through this passage, a strong iron-barred partition was put up at its north-east end.

(c) Printed and framed descriptive notices were set up at the entrance of cave No. 2.

(d) A set of printed copies of the fresco paintings were hitherto exhibited in a show case without glass. To protect the prints from damage the show case was fitted with plate glass.

(e) A stone panel showing the age and name of the monument was set up near the foot of the staircase leading to the caves.

(f) A sign-board engraved on a stone slab was set-up for the guidance of visitors, on the Bagh-Kukshi Road at a point where the cart-track branches off towards the caves.

VI. Annual Up-keep.

34. Annual clearance and petty repairs were carried out to all important groups of monuments already conserved.

VII. Exploration.

(A) Excavations.

35. No excavations were undertaken in the year of report.

(B) Listing of Monuments.

36. Twenty-one monuments or antiquities at eleven different places situated in Amjhera, Bhilsa, Esagarh, Gird and Ujjain Districts were listed during the year under report (see Appendix C) and are briefly described below :—

District Amjhera.

37. *Bagh*.—This small town is already well-known for the rock-cut Buddhist caves in its vicinity. About a mile and a quarter to the south-east of the town, on a hill, is a small structural tank (kund) with natural spring water locally known as Ganga-kui. This place was visited this year in connection with the question of approach road to the caves proposed by the P. W. D.

38. The top of the adjoining hill is strewn over with brick-bats and hence the site seems to be old. At present, however, the only monument standing above ground is a small shrine of Siva within a few yards of the tank. The ruins of the shrine comprise a standing door-frame, Siva-linga inside and some carved debris. The shrine may be contemporary with the Mahakala temple in the neighbourhood, referable to the 10th century A. D.

District Bhilsa.

39. *Maser*.—This is a small village situated on the slopes of a long isolated hill. It lies about 14 miles to the south-east of Basoda. It was visited in consequence of a report of the recovery of two pieces of a stone inscription from the debris of a fallen house. This inscription is described under *Epigraphy*. The only other ancient relics in the locality are a few broken sculptures and carved debris collected on a platform in the field near the village. The platform might be the basement of a small shrine of the 11th century A. D., to which the fragments of sculptures and carved debris evidently belong.

40. About 3 furlongs to the west of Maser at the foot of the same hill has sprung up another hamlet known as Maser Gupha. On examination, the so called *Gupha* (cave) was found to be a false one because it has not been hewn out of the living rock. The hill here is composed of soft sand-stone which has disintegrated owing to natural causes into big sheets and boulders most of which are overhanging. One of such overhanging pieces of rock has been supported on a structural wall and the enclosed space has come to be known as *Gupha*. It is a work of a local *Sadhu* who became famous in the locality about 50 years back and some of his devotees settled here. The *Sadhu's chhatri* also stands nearby.

41. *Sanai*.—This is a small village about 6 miles north of Maser. On either side of the cart-track stand two *sati* stones. One of them bears an inscription which is now illegible. As the figures carved on them are very shallow, the pillars do not appear to be very old.

42. *Siari*.—This is also a small village about 4 miles to the north-west of Sanai. In front of the village and beside a cart-track under a *Pipal* tree, stand some three *sati* stones, one of which is inscribed and bears a date V. S. 1764. The carving is shallow and weak.

District Esagarh.

43. *Benai Kho*.—About a mile to the east of Naderi village and about 6 miles to the south-east of Chanderi lie remains of a few temples in a valley called Benai Kho. Much of the carved and other debris seems to have been taken away and only two or three detached door-frames of 11th century temples are all that is left.

44. *Chor Kho*.—About a mile and a half to the west of Benai Kho is another depression or *Kho* in the hills through which a *nala* flows. At the top of this *Kho* lie the ruins of a dozen shrines some Brahmanical and others

Jaina. They are almost reduced to heaps of debris and may be assigned roughly to the 10th century A. D.

45. *Dhakoni*.—It is a small village about 7 miles to the south of Esagarh on the Esagarh-Chanderi Road. It is known, chiefly, for its large tank which provides a good game of water-fowl. On the outskirts of the village, overlooking the tank stands a ruined temple built in the reign of Durga Singh a Bundela Raja of Chanderi in the year V.S. 1737 (1680 A.D.), as recorded in an inscription set up at its entrance. The temple has no other interesting features, the workmanship being quite ordinary.

46. About a mile to the east of the village in a field, near the canal, is a step-well of about the same age as the temple. It also needs no description, the only interesting feature being an inscription attached to it which also refers to the same Bundela Raja of Chanderi mentioned above. Both the inscriptions are described elsewhere in this report (vide Appendix D. Nos. 5 and 6).

47. *Kulwar*.—This small village lies about two miles north of Dhakoni and on the same road. Almost opposite to the village and near the road is a Sitala Mata *chabutra* on and near which lie a good many fragments of sculptures, *sati* stones and memorial pillars. The sculptures belong roughly to 11th century temples, the memorial pillars to the 13th-14th centuries and the *sati* stones to the 18th century A. D.

District Gird.

48. *Lashkar*.—During the year of report a sculpture, probably a decorative piece of a temple, was noticed lying near the Jai Vilas Palace. Though its provenance is not known, it is a good piece of art of the 12th century A. D. It probably represents a flying Yaksha holding a sword in one hand and an object, probably a book or bundle in the other and is adorned with a fine head-dress.

49. In the Inderganj ward of the city is a building called Sardar Garud Sahib's *wada*, which has lately been converted into a hostel for the students of the College and High School. In the inner yard of this hostel which was probably a garden, stand three Christian tombs that were hitherto unknown being situated inside a private residence. The inmates of the tombs were in the ranks of Maharaja Jayaji Rao Scindia's army.

50. The tombs are almost similar in design which consists of a double platform one upon the other, a tapering block of masonry superimposed on the upper platform and bearing a tablet of epitaph, which in its turn is surmounted with a round column at the top. In one of the three tombs, however, the last two parts (a block of epitaph and round column) are absent.

51. The two complete tombs bear epitaphs from which it is seen that one of them is sacred to Major T. C. Inglis who died in 1867 A. D. aged 53 years and the other to Captain J. H. Martin who died in 1871 A. D. aged 33 years. Close to or rather attached to Martin's grave is the third tomb which has got no tablet. The tomb seems to have been left incomplete.

District Ujjain.

52. *Ujjain*.—A carved lintel of black trap-stone was unearthed this year in the operations of the Town Improvement Trust. It was handed over to the Archæological Department and was exhibited in the collection of old sculptures in the Mahakal temple.

53. Two copper plate inscriptions said to have been found at Gaonri in Narwahal Jagir near Ujjain came to the notice of the Department. The inscriptions on them have been copied and are described in detail under *Epigraphy* below.

VIII. Epigraphy.

54. Ten inscriptions were copied or noticed in the year of report as detailed in Appendix D. Of these eight are in Sanskrit and two in English.

55. Perhaps the most important among the Sanskrit inscriptions are two fragments of a large inscription in old Nagari characters engraved on stone. These were recovered from the debris of a fallen wall of a Brahmana's house at Maser a small village in the Basoda Pargana of the Bhilsa District. (See para 39 above).

56. One of the two fragments which is evidently the beginning portion of the record measures 3' 6" broad by 11" high and contains portions of 10 lines of writing while the other fragment which is an intermediate part measures 2' 3" broad by 1' 1" high and contains portions of 12 lines.

57. Being fragmentary the inscription yields no complete information about its object. The salutation to Siva with which it opens and the three introductory verses which are in praise of the same God and his consort, lead to the conjecture that the record probably belonged to a Saiva temple. The recovered portion does not contain any date. On palæographical grounds however it may be referred to about the 10th century A. D.

58. Points of historical interest gleaned from this fragmentary record are that it mentions a hitherto unknown line of kings of the Sulka or Sulki dynasty¹. The progenitor of this dynasty was Bharadwaja by name who was a *Yama* (god of death) to his foes. His son was Sri Nrisimha, who appears to have been a tributary of a king named Krishnaraja at whose behest he offered a sacrifice in the form of a great war and worshipped the fire of his rage with ghee in the form of the blood of enemies' elephants, and who initiated (the wives of his enemy, a Kalachuri king?) into the vow of widowhood. The name of his son was either Kesari or Gunadhya. Among the contemporaries referred to (as vanquished by this king) are a Latesa (king of Gujrat) and a Kachehhava. Munja and Chachcha (Paramaras?) and Hunas are also mentioned.

59. The next in importance are the two copper-plate grants discovered a few years ago in the digging of a well at Gaonri village in the Narwahal Jagir in the Ujjain District and they are now in the possession of the Jagirdar. They were brought to the notice of the Department, this year, by Pandit Surya Narayanji Vyas a well known astrologer and journalist of Ujjain, to whom our thanks are due.

60. Both the inscriptions are documents of grants of villages made by Vakpatiraja II, the well known Paramara king, who ruled in the last quarter of the 10th century A. D. The genealogy of the king given in these two documents is the same as occurs in his other land grants already published. It mentions Krishnaraja, Vairisimha and Siyaka as his direct ancestors. The *birudas* or titles of king Vakpati namely Prithvi-Vallabha, Srivallabha, Amogha-varsha, etc., enumerated in other grants of this king are specified in these two grants also.

61. One of the two grants is engraved on one side of each of three different copper-plates, the size of which varies from 15¼" to 15½" in length and from

¹This dynasty appears to be different from the Sulki dynasty of Orissa as the names of kings are quite different.

10" to 10¼" in breadth. Each plate is pierced with two holes for holding the seal ring which is now missing. There are 53 lines of writing. The object of the inscription is to register the grant of the village Vanika belonging to Avaraka-bhoga in the Huna-mandala, in charity, by king Vakpatiraja, to different Brahmanas of various gotras on the occasion of a solar eclipse in the month of Karttika in V. S. 1038 (A. D. 981). The document is dated the 10th day of the bright half of the intercalary month of Ashadha in the Vikrama year 1038 i.e., about 8 months after the actual date of the donation and is signed in his own hand by Sri Vakpatiraja-deva at the end. The name of the Officer who issued the order (*Ajna-dapaka*) was Sri Rudraditya. After the writing, at the lower left corner of the last plate is engraved a figure of Garuda holding a serpent.

62. The other inscription is engraved on one side of each of two copper-plates varying from 12⅝" to 12⅝" in length and from 9½" to 9¾" in breadth. Like the plates in the former set, each plate in this also bears two holes for holding the seal ring which in this case also is lost. The lines of writing are 29 in number. The inscription records the grant of the village Kajahichehaka, in charity by king Vakpatiraja II to different Brahmanas of different gotras, on the occasion of *Udagayana* or winter solstice in the month of Magha in V. S. 1043 (A. D. 986). The village granted is described as belonging to the Maddhuka *bhukti* in the Purvva-pathaka of the Ujjayini *Vishaya* in the Avanti-mandala. The grant was made while the king was residing at Purna-pathaka. The document is dated the 13th day of the dark half of the month of Magha in the Vikrama year 1047, that is to say nearly four years after the donation had been formally made.

63. The various place-names mentioned in these grants are yet to be identified. The inscriptions do not furnish any fresh information of historical importance. But there is a striking feature about one of these plates. For, on the back of it is engraved another inscription which though not fully decipherable owing to its extremely obliterated condition still appears to constitute quite another record by itself, dated in V. S. 864 or nearly a century earlier than the Paramara grant engraved on the obverse. Similarly another plate has a short line engraved on its back. This line is evidently contemporary with the principal record on the other face and appears to be a brief title of the same.

64. The inscriptions of Bundelas are in corrupt Sanskrit and engraved in degenerate Nagari script. One of these is on a ruined temple and the other on a *baodi* in village Dhakoni near Esagarh and refer to construction of the respective monuments in the reign of the Bundela Raja Durga Singh (1663-1681 A. D.) of Chanderi.

65. The remaining Sanskrit inscriptions are on *sati* stones and are illegible owing to their worn-out condition. One of them bears the date V. S. 1764.

66. The inscriptions in English are merely epitaphs on tombs and refer to the deaths of Major T. C. Inglis and Capt. J. H. Martin of H. H. the Maharaja Scindia's army, who died in A. D. 1867 and 1871 respectively. These do not mention the name of the Ruler but in consideration of the dates given, they belong to the reign of H. H. the Maharaja Jayaji Rao Scindia, Alijah Bahadur (A. D. 1843-1886).

IX. Numismatics.

67. Three hundred and ten silver, one hundred and seventy-eight copper and two billon (mixed metal) or 490 coins in all were examined

during the year under report. Of these, silver and copper coins were received as treasure-trove finds from Masari (District Gird) and Pichhore (District Narwar), while the two mixed metal pieces which are, in fact, electron casts of the original coins of king Lalitaditya Muktapida (circa 700 A. D.) were received from the Secretary, Coin Committee, as present from the U. P. Government.

68. The silver find contains 310 coins of the Mugal Emperors—Akbar, Jahangir, Shahjahan, Aurangzeb and Murad Baksh. Being very badly damaged they presented no good or new specimens. The only mint name traceable was that of Lahore on some of the coins, while a complete date could not be deciphered on any of them.

69. The copper hoard was still more badly mutilated as most of the coins were simply plain worn-out pieces of metal. They are mostly coins of the Scindias. These were to be returned as the Court had decided to give them back to the claimant. Thus out of all the coins treated, four silver and two mixed metal coins were added to the Museum collection as shown in Appendix F and the rest disposed of for good. For further details reference may be made to Appendix E.

X. Archæological Institutions.

(A) Gwalior Museum.

70. Two stone inscriptions, twelve stone sculptures, two brass images, thirty-nine miniature paintings, four silver coins, two electron casts of coins, five impressions of copper plates or sixty-six antiquities in all were added to the Museum in the year under notice and are set forth in Appendix F. Out of the above acquisitions, the two brass images were purchased from the collection of Rai Bahadur Pandit Radha Krishna of Muttra. Two electron casts of coins were presented by the U. P. Government to whom our best thanks are due. The remaining acquisitions were made from within the State.

71. The Gwalior Archæological Museum is now an important and popular institution, and few of the numerous visitors to this capital town leave this place without seeing it. The visitors' book kept in the Museum bears signatures and remarks of appreciation of about eight hundred connoisseurs and dilettanti from different parts of the world but in fact, the actual number of visitors being far greater than that noted above, since some of them either do not choose to sign or being members of a party leave this task to their secretary or to their guide.

72. Out of this vast number of visitors represented in the Visit Book, some 125 are foreigners who came to India as tourists. They belong to different countries of the globe such as Switzerland, Germany (Zürich, Hamburg and Berlin), France (Paris), United States of America (San Francisco, Boston, Chicago, Brooklyn and New York), Denmark, England (London), Africa (Mombasa), China (Shanghai) and Baluchistan. The Indian visitors represent almost all the provinces of India, Burma and Ceylon including French and Dutch possessions in India.

73. The following may be mentioned as some of the distinguished visitors to the Museum during the year under notice :—

(1) J. A. W. Sampson, Esq., Colonial Minister, Africa, (2) Lady Delegates to the all-Asian Women's Conference, (3) H. Hergreaves, Esq., Offg. Director-General of Archæology in India, (4) C. Jinarajadasa, Adyar, (5) Sir J. J. Modi, K.T., LL.D., etc. of Bombay, (6) Rao Bahadur Vaidya, M.B.E.,

Revenue Minister, Jind State, (7) R. N. Sharma, M.R.A.S., R.S.M., of Lucknow, and the undernoted officials of the State :—

(1) H. M. Bull, Esq., Principal, Victoria College, (2) E. J. Hope, Esq., Technical Adviser, G. L. Ry., (3) C. W. C. Carson, Esq., Investment Officer, (4) C. M. Tembe, Esq., Director of State Gardens, (5) K. B. Dongre, Esq., I. G. of Records, (6) Mr. H. G. Waterfield, Inspector-General of Police.

(B) Ujjain Museum.

74. It will appear from last year's report that a collection of antiquities was started for the proposed Museum at Ujjain and it was to be continued as the funds permit. But due to general strain on funds as stated elsewhere in this report nothing material could be done in this direction during the year. One stone sculpture recovered during the operations of the City Improvement Scheme was, however, added to this collection.

XI. Miscellaneous.

75. (a) *Distinguished Visitors to Monuments.*—On account of the systematic efforts in the direction of advertising the important Archæological Monuments of the State, some of the groups of the monuments in the districts have now become popular and the number of visitors to them is appreciably on the increase. The following names are taken from the Visitors' Book kept at Bagh Caves which are in the remote interior :—

Dewan Sahibs of Indore, Jhabua, Badwani States and the Administrator of Jobat State, all of the Central India Agency. Revenue Minister, Jhabua; Muntazim Bahadur E. B. Kauley, Indore; Prof. Kulkarni and a party of Elphinstone College, Bombay; Principal of the Maharaja's College, Dhar and a party of the Sardars of the Dhar State. The following officials of the Gwalior State also visited the caves during the year under notice :—

Sardar M. N. Shitole, Offg. Home Member; Rao Bahadur Bapu Rao Pawar, Member for Agriculture; Rao Sahib L. B. Muley, Member for Education and Municipalities; Dr. Y. G. Apte, Administrative Officer, P. W. D.; S. S. Gaur, Esq., Secretary, Home Department; K. B. Dongre, Esq., Inspector-General of Records; Rai Bahadur S. N. Bhaduri, Technical Adviser, P. W. D.; V. S. Dube, Esq., Mining Expert, and R. N. Sharma, Divisional Officer, Forests.

76. Some of the important monuments such as Udaygiri caves near Bhilsa and the caves at Bagh badly need approach roads connecting them with trunk roads, proposals for which have already been made. The completion of these roads is likely to increase considerably the number of visitors.

77. (b) *Demonstration at Bagh (District Amjhera).*—Bagh was the scene of a largely attended Conference of the Bhils and Bhilalas the predominating classes of people inhabiting this part of the country. They met here to deliberate on their educational and social progress under the auspices of the Gwalior Government. The Archæological Department, taking advantage of this mass gathering, gave a magic lantern show on its activities in the various lines of Archæology and at the same time made an appeal for the co-operation of the public. The show caused an awakening and appealed immensely to this gathering which dispersed with hearts filled with deep love and regard for the relics of the past and brought to them the advantages of importance and need for Archæology.

78. (c) *Appreciation of the Department's Services.*—As stated in last year's report, the Department arranged an exhibition with the co-opera-

tion of the conveners of the 12th session of the Indian Historical Records Commission at Gwalior. This met general approbation and in recognition of this modest service all the members of the Department engaged in the work were awarded in the first instance certificates of merit and later on, on the recommendation of the Inspector-General of Records were honoured with poshak and cash rewards on the auspicious occasion of His Highness' Birthday Darbar.

79. Members of the Department embrace this opportunity of humbly placing on record their best thanks to the authorities concerned for the recognition of their services.

Poshak.

- (1) M. B. Garde, Superintendent of Archæology.

Cash Rewards.

	Rs.
(1) Ramsingh Saksena, Inspector	75
(2) Lachhmi Prasad Verma, General Assistant	60
(3) R. S. Khandalkar, Officer, Correspondence	50

XII. Photographs and Drawings.

80. One hundred and thirty-two photographs were taken and over thirteen hundred bromide photo-prints from the new and old negatives were prepared during the year under notice. The above prints were made (a) for the usual set required for annual record, (b) for the Darbar Albums submitted annually, (c) for making two sets of albums of photographs of important monuments in the State for the reference of dilettanti, (d) for making picture post-cards of some monuments, (e) for reference charts and (f) for illustrating the works of various authors.

81. The persons who were supplied with the prints for the last named purpose are:—

- (1) Miss Alice Bonner of America.
- (2) Miss Medelin Blitzstein, Philadelphia, U. S. A.
- (3) Dr. Coomaraswamy, Boston, U. S. A.
- (4) D. Stansly, Canton, China.
- (5) Dr. S. K. Chatterji, Calcutta University.
- (6) Swami Vidyanand of Jasdan State, Kathiawar.
- (7) Prof. R. N. Bhagwat, St. Xavier's College, Bombay.
- (8) Mr. Chiplunkar of Poona.
- (9) Mr. Kamakhya Datta Ram of Lucknow.
- (10) Mr. P. V. Dalal, Ujjain.
- (11) Mess President, 5/6 Rajputana Rifles, Aurangabad.

82. Sixty-four lantern slides illustrating various relics and antiquities were also made.

83. Seventeen drawings and tracings were made for the use of the Department for illustrating schemes developed or submitted for consideration.

84. For detailed list of photo and picture post-card negatives, lantern slides and drawings made, see Appendices G, H and I respectively.

XIII. Office Library.

85. One hundred and twenty-nine volumes were added to the office library of the Superintendent of Archaeology in the year under report and comprise books on different subjects such as History, Art, Architecture and allied subjects. Of these 88 were purchased and the rest were received as presents from the Government of India, Provincial Governments, Governments of Indian States and other private institutions to whom our thanks are due. A detailed list of the above books is given in Appendix J.

86. The Department is also endeavouring to start a system of mutual exchange of its publications with those bodies that have no such dealings with the Department upto now. The object in view is an economic acquisition of books for the library and also that of keeping the Department in touch with institutions of similar aims and objects. During the year under notice such exchange was established with the following institutions :—

- (1) Indore Museum, Indore.
- (2) Journal of Indian History, Madras.
- (3) Connemara Public Library, Madras.
- (4) Behar and Orissa Research Society, Patna.
- (5) Andhra Historical Research Society.

XIV. Income and Expenditure.

87. The expenditure incurred under various heads of the budget by the Department and the income realized is set forth in Appendices K and L respectively. Thus the annual expenditure amounted to Rs. 31,301-2-10 and the income from various sources to Rs. 252-9-4 during the year.

XV. Concluding Remarks.

88. The Department thankfully acknowledges its indebtedness, for co-operation in its work, to the Municipal Board, Lashkar, for providing and running the electric installation at the Chhatri of Maharani Lakshmibai of Jhansi and to the Subas and Engineers of Districts Bhilsa, Esagarh, Ujjain and Amjhera for helping the Department in ways more than one.

89. In conclusion the Department owes a deep debt of gratitude to Shrimant Khase Sahib Pawar and Major Sardar M. N. Shitole Sahib, the permanent and the Offg. Home Members, respectively, due to whose able direction, valuable suggestions and unfailing courtesy and help it could discharge its duties efficiently and successfully.

R. S. SAKSENA,

Offg. Superintendent of Archaeology,

Gwalior State.

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APPENDIX

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PART II.

APPENDIX A.

**Tour Diary of the Superintendent of Archæology, Gwalior State,
for the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.**

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
July 1930.		
4th-6th.	Gwalior to Bagh Caves.	
7th.	Bagh to Mhow.	
8th.	Mhow to Ujjain.	
9th-10th.	Ujjain to Gwalior.	
11th.	Gwalior to Surwaya <i>via</i> Shivpuri.	
12th.	Halt at Surwaya.	
13th.	Surwaya to Gwalior.	
October 1930.		
22nd.	Gwalior to Shivpuri.	
23rd.	Shivpuri to Surwaya and back.	
24th.	Shivpuri to Sesai and back.	
25th.	Shivpuri to Gwalior.	
December 1930.		
15th-16th.	Gwalior to Patna.	
16th-24th.	Halt at Patna.	
24th-25th.	Patna to Gwalior.	
January 1931.		
7th.	Gwalior to Antri and Dabra.	
8th.	Dabra to Pawaya and back.	
9th.	Dabra to Gwalior.	
12th.	Gwalior to Padhavli <i>via</i> Rithora.	
13th.	Padhavli to Sanichara <i>via</i> Bharoli.	
14th.	Sanichara to Paroli and then to Gwalior.	

APPENDIX A—(contd.)

Date, month and year.	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS
February 1931.		
2nd.	Gwalior to Bhind.	
3rd.	Bhind to Kherhat and back.	
4th.	Bhind to Barai and back to Gwalior.	
March 1931.		
10th-11th.	Gwalior to Chanderi <i>via</i> Mungaoli.	
12th.	Halt at Chanderi.	
13th.	Chanderi to Naderi and back.	
14th.	Chanderi to Thoban and back.	
15th.	Chanderi to Budhi Chanderi and back.	
16th.	Chanderi to Gwalior <i>via</i> Mungaoli.	
20th.	Gwalior to Shivpuri.	
21st.	Shivpuri to Palpur <i>via</i> Pohri and Paronda.	
22nd.	Palpur to Shivpuri.	
23rd.	Shivpuri to Gwalior.	
24th-25th.	Gwalior to Ujjain.	
26th.	Ujjain to Bagh.	
27th.	Bagh to Sardarpur.	
28th.	Sardarpur to Bagh Caves.	
29th-30th.	Halt at Bagh Caves.	
31st.	Bagh Caves to Mhow.	
April 1931.		
1st-2nd.	Mhow to Mandasor.	
3rd.	Halt at Mandasor.	
4th-5th.	Mandasor to Gwalior.	
23rd.	Gwalior to Narwar <i>via</i> Satanwada.	
24th.	Narwar to Shivpuri.	
25th	Shivpuri to Chanderi <i>via</i> Esagarh.	

APPENDIX A.—(concl'd.)

Date, month and year	Movements and Halts.	REMARKS.
25th.	Chanderi to Panchamnagar and back.	
26th.	Halt at Chanderi.	
27th.	Chanderi to Shivpuri <i>via</i> Esagarh.	
28th.	Shivpuri to Surwaya and back	
29th.	Shivpuri to Gwalior.	
May 1931.		
5th.	Gwalior to Bhind.	
6th.	Bhind to Kherhat and back.	
7th.	Bhind to Gwalior.	
Offg. Superintendent's Tour Diary.		
June 1931.		
12th-13th.	Gwalior to Chanderi.	
14th-15th.	Chanderi to Ujjain.	
16th.	Ujjain to Mandasor.	
17th.	Mandasor to Bagh <i>via</i> Mhow.	
18th.	Bagh to Bagh Caves.	
19th-21st.	Halt at Bagh Caves.	
22nd.	Bagh Caves to Bagh.	
23rd.	Bagh to Ujjain.	
24th.	Ujjain to Bhilsa.	
25th.	Bhilsa to Gwalior	

List of Monuments Conserved during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

No.	Place.	Particulars.	AMOUNT SANCTIONED.		TOTAL.	AMOUNT SPENT		TOTAL.	REMARKS
			Current year.	Last year.		Current year.	Last year.		
			Rs. a. p.		Rs. a. p.			Rs. a. p.	
1	Badoli ..	Petty works to Monuments ..	232 0 0	..	232 0 0	222 5 0	..	222 5 0	
2	Bagh ..	Repairs to Caves ..	8,000 0 0	..	8,000 0 0	7,230 2 10	..	7,230 2 10	
3	Bhilsa ..	Petty works to Monuments ..	130 0 0	..	130 0 0	126 10 2	..	126 10 2	
4	Chanderi ..	Johar Monument ..	550 0 0	..	550 0 0	135 13 10	..	135 13 10	
5	Gwalior ..	Gujari Mahal ..	340 0 0	..	340 0 0	339 10 3	..	339 10 3	
6	Kherhat ..	Brick Temple ..	390 0 0	..	390 0 0	376 9 9	..	376 9 9	
7	Lashkar ..	Chhatri of Maharani of Jhansi.	773 0 0	..	773 0 0	730 2 0	..	730 2 0	
8	Mandasor.	Yasodharman's pillars and minor monuments.	655 0 0	..	655 0 0	652 2 3	..	652 2 3	
9	Narwar ..	Armenian tombs ..	2 0 0	..	2 0 0	2 0 0	..	2 0 0	
10	Padhavli ...	Ancient temple in Garhi ..	1,000 0 0	..	1,000 0 0	939 10 6	..	939 10 6	
		Total ..	12,072 0 0	..	12,072 0 0	10,755 2 7	..	10,755 2 7	

APPENDIX C.

Monuments Listed during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

S. No.	Place.	Particulars.	Class.	REMARKS
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh.	Remains of an old shrine of Siva near Ganga Kui.	III	
District Bhilsa.				
2	Maser.	Remnants of a small temple and sculptures near the village.	I	
3-4	..	Pieces of inscribed stone.	II	
5-6	Sanai.	Two <i>sati</i> stones, one of which is inscribed.	III	
7	Siari.	An inscribed <i>sati</i> stone.	III	
8	..	Another inscribed <i>sati</i> stone.	III	
District Esagarh.				
9	Benai Kho.	Remains of a few old Brahmanical temples	III	
10	Chor Kho.	.. of a few Jaina temples.	III	
11	..	.. of a few Brahmanical temples.	III	
12	Dhakoni.	A deserted temple with an inscription of Bundela Raja of Chanderi.	III	
13	..	A step-well with an inscription of the Bundela Raja of Chanderi.	III	
14	Kulwar.	A memorial pillar.	III	
15	..	A group of sculptures near above.	III	
District Gird (Gwalior).				
16	Lashkar.	A loose sculpture of a <i>Yaksha</i> in Phoolbag near Jai Vilas Palace.	III	
17	..	A Christian tomb sacred to Major T. C. Inglis, died A. D. 1867.	III	
18	..	A Christian tomb sacred to Capt. Martin, died A. D. 1871.	III	
19	..	A Christian tomb close to the above (incomplete).	III	
District Ujjain.				
20-21	Ujjain.	Two copper-plate inscriptions in the possession of a Jagirdar.	I	

APPENDIX D.

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

Serial No.	Local No.	Locality	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
District Bhilsa.										
1		Maser.	On a stone slab ..	10	Old Nagari.	Sanskrit.	Narasimha.	..	Owing to the fragmentary condition, its purport is not clear. It refers to a certain King Narasimha of Sulki dynasty, who overpowered Krishnaraja, a Kalachuri King. He has been profusely eulogised for this victory.	Right side portion of the inscription is broken and lost.
2		..	On another stone slab ..	11	..	..	..	..	Being fragmentary and damaged, the purport is not clear.	..
3		Sanai.	On a <i>sati</i> stone ..	6	Nagari (crude).	..	..	V. S. 17—?	Worn-out and illegible.	Not copied.
4		..		7	..	..	..	V. S. 1764		..
District Esagarh.										
5		Siari. Dhakoni.	On a slab in a niche to the left side of the main entrance to a ruined temple.	6	..	..	Durga Singh.	V. S. 1737	Refers to the construction of a temple at Dhakoni, Sarkar Chandari, in the reign of Durga Singh, a Bundela Raja of Chandari (1663-1687 A. D.)	

APPENDIX D.—(contd.)

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

Serial No.	Local No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
6		Dhakoni.	District Esagarh (contd) On a slab in a niche in the step-well in a field opposite the village near a canal.	6	Nagari (crude).	Sanskrit.	Durga Singh.	V. S. 1743	Records the construction of a step-well in memory of a deceased girl in the reign of Durga Singh, a Bundela Raja of Chanderi.	Not copied.
7 (a)		Lashkar.	District Gird. On a slab built up in a tomb in the yard of the New Boarding House, Inderganj.	9	Roman.	English.	Maharaja Scindia.	1867 A. D.	It is an epitaph and records the death of Major T. C. Inglis on the 4th April 1867, who was in the service of H. H. the Maharaja Scindia (Jayajirao) and was aged 53 years.	"
(b)		"	On the same tablet.	4	Nastaliq.	Urdu.	"	"	Urdu version of the above.	"
(c)		"	"	3	Nagari.	Hindi.	"	"	Hindi transcript of the above.	"
8		"	On a slab built up in another tomb in the same premises.	7	Roman.	English.	"	1871 A. D.	It is also an epitaph and records the death of Captain Martin on the 3rd April 1871, aged 33 years. He was also in the service of H. H. the Maharaja Scindia's Army.	"

List of Inscriptions Copied or Noticed during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

Serial No.	Local No.	Locality.	Object Inscribed.	Number of Lines.	Script.	Language.	Name of King.	Date.	Purport.	REMARKS.
9		Ujjain.	District Ujjain. Copper plate inscription.	53	Old Nagari.	Sanskrit.	Vakapati- raja II.	V. S. 1038 <i>Adhik,</i> Ashadha <i>stuti</i> 10.	Records the grant of a village Vanika ? to Brahmana pilgrims of different <i>gotras</i> on the auspicious occasion of a solar eclipse in the month of Karttika, V. S. 1038.	Three plates make one complete record
10				29	"	"	"	V. S. 1047 Magha <i>vadi</i> 13.	Records the grant of a village named Bhichhuka ? in <i>Avanti-mandala</i> , to Brahmana pilgrims on the sacred occasion of Udagayana or winter solstice in the month of Magh, V. S. 1043.	The record comprises itself in two separate plates.

APPENDIX E.

List of Coins Examined during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

S. No.	Particulars.	Metal.	Mint or type.	Date.	No. of coins.
1	Lalituditya Muktapida circa 700 A. D.	Electron.	..	..	2 ✓
2	Akbar the great	Silver.	..	..	33
3	Akbar the great (another type) ..	..	..	..	7
4	Jahangir	..	Lahore.	..	28
5	Shahjahan	..	..	..	157
6	Aurangzeb	..	..	..	37
7	Murad Baksha	..	..	..	1
8	Mutilated	..	..	..	47
9	Do.	Copper.	..	..	178
Total ..					490

**List of Antiquities Added to the Museum of Archæology at Gwalior, in
Samvat 1987, Year 1930-31.**

S. No.	Description.	Size.	REMARKS
Paintings.			
1	A young man seated along an ottoman, smoking and gazing steadfastly at a woman who is talking to her maids.	9½" × 8¼"	
2	Two females standing on the bank of a tank, one of them is a maid and is probably extolling the beauty of her mistress.	Do.	
3	A lady standing, surrounded by seven maids, is viewing a youth standing on her right side.	9¼" × 8½"	
4	A man standing on the right, and four females on the left. The mistress with her hand raised to the head accosts with her maids.	Do.	
5	A male and female standing face to face, in an amorous mood, in an open courtyard.	9¼" × 8½"	
6	A male and female looking at each other from windows of the distant rooms; they are pointed at by two females standing below.	9½" × 8½"	
7	Krishna is seated with his left leg hung down, with a milk-maid in his front. Radha is seated in another room, in a morose mood.	9" × 8¼"	
8	A mistress half standing, kneeling against an ottoman with her maid standing in front to the right.	9½" × 8¼"	
9	Above in a window of a room sits a male, three females are seated on the opposite side. Below stand two females in front talking to each other. On both sides stands a group of six females and two males.	9" × 8½"	
10	A lady with two maids standing towards back, sees a man standing in front to her right. Above on the left is a scene of a duel, each with a sword and a shield in hand.	9½" × 8¼"	
11	A maid pointing her mistress to her lover who stands to her right.	9¼" × 8¼"	
12	A young man taking off his weapons and ornaments handing them over to his beloved. Two females looking at this from the right-side room.	9¼" × 8¼"	
13	Krishna seated on a carpet along an ottoman facing right. Two females stand on the right side talking.	Do.	
14	A young man is seeing a female dressing her hair and probably telling her attendants of her extraordinary beauty.	9½" × 8¼"	
15	A youth stands in a park, with a maid standing close by, watching the pranks of his beloved playing with a flower.	9½" × 9"	

APPENDIX F.—(contd.)

S. No.	Description.	Size.	REMARKS
16	A man with a black turban and shallow mustaches, standing with a female beside him. On the right stands a female and above is a grove of green grass.	9½" × 8½"	
17	Scene of varandah in a house. A man and a woman standing face to face, the former clasping her hand and putting his right arm on her shoulder.	9" × 8½"	
18	Krishna stands facing Radha, holding a rose in his hand. A milk-maid looks at in amazement.	8½" × 8½"	
19	Krishna playing on flute. Two females eagerly listening to it.	9½" × 8½"	
20	A female seated along an ottoman in contemplation. Another stands before her as if questioning about her condition.	9½" × 8¾"	
21	Krishna and Radha meeting in a thick grove. Two of her maids watch this and whisper to each other.	Do.	
22	Krishna sits along an ottoman hanging down his left leg. Radhika sits in her parlour in displeasure, with a maid trying to appease her.	8½" × 9½"	
23	Krishna is seated above, holding a bird. Radha sits below in the right. Two of her companions stand before her, whispering.	7" × 8½"	
24	Three men surround a youth who is gazing a female seated in a room, attended by two maids at her back. Two females stand below and two rows of trees are seen above.	7" × 8½"	
25	Krishna stands on the right; Radha stands with two companions in a room, with her face turned to him.	8" × 7"	
26	Krishna stands in a room on the 1st floor with Radha standing before him. Two females descend down the steps and two others stand apart pointing.	8½" × 8½"	
27	A mistress is seated on her knees along an ottoman with her maid sitting beside her.	8¾" × 7½"	
28	A man with a black turban and with a flower in his left hand, stands talking to the maid. A female sits on the left along an ottoman.	7½" × 7"	
29	A man and a woman stand on the left; two females stand on the right. A mistress sits along an ottoman with one maid on the left and two on the right side. Four females are seated below, one playing on a drum, another on tabor. A candle is burning below.	9½" × 12"	
30	A princess plays on a guitar, sitting along an ottoman bedecked with ornaments on her person.	5½" × 8"	
31	A brave youth stands with a spear, a sword and a shield in his hand with a female standing at his back with her face cast down. Four females are dancing on the left. Two females lie prostrate below. Six male heads are seen kept in a tub, side by side, beside which stands another woman in dejection.	8½" × 10"	

APPENDIX F.—(contd.)

S. No.	Description.	Size.	REMARKS
32	A Mahomedan chief riding an elephant with a sword and a shield. He has a thick black beard and wears a huge turban.	9" × 11"	
33	An armoured Mahomedan with a long beard and a spear in his hand rides on a horse. A sword hangs down from his left.	9½" × 13"	
34	An ascetic sits on the lion's skin with a rosary in his hand under the shade of a tree. Long matted hair and white long beard hangs down the waist and navel. A disciple sits writing on a piece of wood.	6" × 8½"	
35	A female is playing on a tabor and singing to its accompaniment.	10" × 14½"	
36	Maharani Baija Bai in a green sari, sits with legs crosswise holding a betel.	10" × 14½"	
37	Maharaja Jankoji Rao Scindia with a green wrapper, a white <i>anga</i> and a red Marathi turban, holding a sword.	10" × 13½"	
38	Maharaja Daulat Rao Scindia seated along an ottoman on a cushion. A sword with a black sheath is placed below. Two attendants with a fly-whisk and a spit-pot stand to his left side.	9½" × 11½"	
39	A Maratha Sardar riding a white pink horse with a lance in his right hand. He wears a red turban and a red <i>anga</i> .	8½" × 10½"	
Sculptures.			
40	A man killing a lion brought from Padhavli.	4'5" × 1'4" × 3"	
41	A man with a sword and a dagger and a circle on its three sides brought from Padhavli.	4' × 1'4" × 3"	
42	A <i>sati</i> stone brought from Padhavli.	6' × 2' × 10"	
43	A <i>sati</i> stone inscribed.	5'7" × 1' × 7"	
44	A piece of stone having nine male figures on it brought from Padhavli.	3'4" × 1'2" × 8"	
45	A piece of stone having eight male figures on it, brought from Padhavli.	3'4" × 1'2" × 8"	
46	A dome brought from Padhavli.	} 11'7"	
47	A dome brought from Padhavli.		
48	A memorial stone, brought from Bara.	6' × 1'3" × 6"	

APPENDIX F.—(concl'd.)

S. No.	Description.	Size.	REMARKS
49	An inscribed memorial stone brought from Rithora.	5'4" × 4' × 9"	
50	A Jaina image brought from Rithora.	3' × 10" × 6"	
51	A Jaina image brought from Rithora.	3' × 10" × 6"	
Inscriptions.			
52	A fragment of a stone inscription in old Nagari characters brought from Maser.	3'5" × 11" × 4"	
53	Do. (another piece).	2'5" × 1'1" × 4½"	
Impressions.			
54-56	Impressions of copper—plate inscriptions from Ujjain. A land grant of Vakpati II of Dhar, dated V. S. 1038.		
57-58	Do. Do. dated V. S. 1047.		
Coins.			
59-60	Coins of Lalitaditya Muktapida (circa 700 A. D.) Billon.		
61	Akbar the great, silver coin of Lahore Mint and Ilahi year 5.		
62-63	Jahangir, silver coins of Lahore Mint and Ilahi year 6 and 10.		
64	Murad Baksh s/o Shahjahan, Silver coin.		
Metal Images.			
65	Image of a god Brass.		
66	Image of a goddess Copper.		
Ujjain Museum of Archæology.			
67	A piece of black trap lintel of a door frame having the sculpture of Vishnu brought from Ujjain city.	2½ × 1½ × ½	

List of Photo Negatives Taken during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

Serial No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	Size.	Remarks.
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh.	Cave No. 4, frieze after repair showing new supports.	Full.	
2	"	Cave No. 4, pillar after repair.	"	
3	"	" " two pillars after repair.	"	
4	"	" " another pillar after repair.	Half.	
5	"	" " " " " "	"	
District Bhind.				
6	Kherhat.	Brick temple, general view after repair from S. E.	Full.	
7	"	Brick temple back view from S. W.	"	
8	"	" " near view "	Half.	
9	"	" " " " N. E.	Full.	
10	"	An image of Siva and Parvati, in the brick temple.	"	
11	"	Images in open-air collection near " "	Half.	
12	"	Image of Vishnu near brick temple.	"	
13	"	" Siva " "	"	
District Esagarh.				
14	Kulwar.	A memorial pillar.	Quarter.	
District Gird (Gwalior).				
15	Gwalior.	Jama Masjid from N. E.	Full.	
16	"	" " inscription.	"	
17	"	" " another inscription.	"	
18	"	A mosque near Delhi gate from S. W.	"	
19	"	Tombs with carved enclosures near Khandara Khan's mosque.	"	
20	"	Khandara Khan's mosque, near view from south.	"	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	Size.	REMARKS.
21	Archæological Museum.	A copper image of a goddess, front view.	Half.	
22	"	" " " side view.	"	
23	"	" " " back view.	"	
24	"	A brass image of a god, front view.	"	
25	"	" " " back view.	"	
26	Lashkar.	Marble canopy and statue of Maharani Sakhyaraja, general view.	Full.	
27	"	Marble canopy and statue of Maharani Sakhyaraja, front view.	"	
28	"	Marble canopy and statue of Maharani Sakhyaraja, front view.	"	Duplicate.
29	"	Jal-bihar in King George Park, general view	"	
30	"	Nau-talao guest-house, from S. E.	"	
31	"	Jaivilas Palace, general view from S. E.	"	
32	"	" " interior, general view from courtyard.	"	
33	"	A gun from Narwar near <i>Nadi</i> Darwaza.	"	
34	"	A glass chandelier in the inner portico of Jaivilas Palace.	"	
35	"	Another gun from Bhilsa in front of the Palace near Lalitpur Darwaza.	"	
36	"	Another gun from Bhilsa, near view.	"	
37	"	" " " near view.	"	Duplicate.
38	"	" " " inscription on the gun.	"	
39	"	<i>Chhatri</i> of Maharaja Daulat Rao Scindia.	"	
40	"	" " " Jankoji Rao Scindia.	"	
41	"	" " " Jayaji Rao Scindia.	"	
42	"	" " " Jayaji Rao showing carved work.	"	
43	"	<i>Chhatri</i> of Maharaja Jayaji Rao showing carved work.	"	Duplicate.

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	Size.	REMARKS
44	Lashkar.	<i>Chhatri</i> of Maharaja Jayaji Rao showing carved work.	Full.	Duplicate.
45	"	Gorkhi or old Palace at Bada from inside.	"	
46	"	" <i>Devaghar</i> from S. E.	"	
47	"	Jayaji Chowk, general view from N. W.	"	
48	"	Statue of Maharaja Jayaji Rao Scindia in Jayaji Chowk, near view from west.	"	
49	"	Statue of Maharaja Jayaji Rao Scindia in Jayaji Chowk, near view from east.	"	
50	"	General Post Office in Jayaji Chowk.	"	
51	"	Sarafa Bazar, general view.	"	
52	"	" " " duplicate.	"	
53	"	Jali work (a <i>Jharokha</i>) in a building in Sarafa Bazar.	"	
54	"	Jali work (a <i>Jharokha</i>) in another building.	Half.	
55	"	Kampoo Kothi.	Full.	
56	"	Jaya Arogya Hospital, front view.	"	
57	"	" " " side view.	"	
58	"	Victoria College, from north-east.	"	
59	"	" " " detail.	"	
60	"	Memorial of Mahadji Scindia, general view.	"	
61	"	Memorial of Mahadji Scindia, another view.	"	
62	"	Statue of Mahadji Scindia, general view.	Half.	
63	"	Statue of Mahadji Scindia, back view.	"	
64	"	Elgin Club.	Full.	
65	"	Jinsi building, from south-west.	"	
66	"	" " " south-east.	"	
67	"	Christian tombs in the Inderganj Boarding House, general view.	"	
68	"	Christian tombs in the Inderganj Boarding House, near view.	"	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	Size.	REMARKS
69	Lashkar.	Another Christian tomb, near view.	Half.	
70	"	Grand Hotel, from south-west.	Full.	
71	"	Sakhya Vilas Palace, view.	"	
72	"	A carved stone lamp-post in the garden of Sakhya Vilas.	"	
73	Pawaya.	Fragment of a lintel of <i>torana</i> gateway.	"	
74	"	" showing Trivikrama <i>avatara</i> .	"	
75	"	" " Vamana <i>avalara</i> .	"	
76	"	" " music and dance.	"	
77	"	" " another side.	"	
78	"	" " (duplicate).	"	
79	"	" " Shadanan.	"	
80	"	" " Samudra Manthan.	"	
District Mandasor.				
81	Sondni.	Yasodharman's pillars after conservation, view from west.	Quarter.	
82	"	Yasodharman's pillars after conservation, view from north-west.	"	
District Narwar.				
83	Sesai.	A Jaina image.	Quarter.	
District Tonwarghar.				
84	Padhavli.	Temple in <i>Garhi</i> , after repair, front view from west.	Full.	
85	"	Temple in <i>Garhi</i> , corner view from north-west.	"	
86	"	Temple in <i>Garhi</i> , corner view from south-west.	"	
87	"	Temple in <i>Garhi</i> , pillars in the interior.	"	
88	"	" " ceiling.	"	
89	"	" " another ceiling.	"	

APPENDIX G.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	Size.	REMARKS.
90	Padhavli.	Temple in <i>Garhi</i> , another ceiling.	Full.	
91	"	" " " " "	"	
92	"	" " an image of Surya.	"	
93	"	" " " (duplicate).	"	
94	"	" " interior detail.	"	
95	"	" " " "	"	
96	"	" " interior detail, after repairs,	"	
97	"	" " " "	"	
98	"	" " " "	"	
99	"	" " " "	"	
100	"	" " " "	"	
101	"	" " " "	"	
102	"	" " " "	"	
103	"	" " " "	"	
Miscellaneous.				
<i>(Paintings.)</i>				
104	Archæological Museum.	A young man smoking and two females.	Half.	
105	"	Krishna playing <i>Murli</i> and two females listening.	"	
106	"	A mistress and her maid.	"	
107	"	Maharani Baija Bai Scindia.	"	
108	"	Maharaja Jankoji Rao Scindia.	"	
109	"	Maharaja Daulat Rao Scindia.	"	
110	"	A young man giving weapons to her beloved.	"	
111	"	A Mahomedan chief riding on an elephant.	"	
112	"	A princess playing on a guitar.	"	
113-15	"	Copper-plate inscription from Ujjain in three pieces, full view.	Full.	
116-18	"	Copper-plate inscription text.	"	

APPENDIX G.—(concl.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	Size	REMARKS.
119-20	Archæological Museum.	Another copper-plate inscription in two pieces, full view.	Full.	
121-22	"	Copper-plate inscription text.	"	
123-27	"	Copper-plate, another inscription on its back.	"	
128	"	Fragment of inscription from Maser.	Quarter.	
129	"	A chart presented to H. H. Maharaja on the occasion of birthday celebration on 27th October 1930, showing important places of Archæological interest with an illustration of leading monument from each place.	Full.	
130	"	A map of Gwalior State showing important places of Archæological interest, 1930.	"	
131	"	Painting showing a <i>Johar</i> ceremony.	Quarter.	
132	"	Painting showing Tansen, his Guru(?) and Akbar.	"	
Copying Negatives for Picture Post-Cards				
District Amjhera.				
1	Bagh.	Cave No. 4. a frieze.	Post-Card.	
District Bhilsa.				
2	Udayagiri.	Cave No. 5. Varaha.	"	
3	Udaypur.	Udayesvar temple, back view.	"	
4	"	" " " (duplicate).	"	
District Esagarh.				
5	Chanderi.	Fort, general view.	"	
6	"	Nizamuddin's graveyard, a carved Mihrab.	"	
District Gird.				
7	Gwalior Fort.	Man Singh's Palace, south face.	"	
8	" "	A Jaina image.	"	
9	Gwalior.	Tomb of Muhammad Ghaus, general view.	"	
District Narwar.				
10	Surwaya.	Ceiling of Temple No. 1.	"	
District Ujjain.				
11	Ujjain.	Astronomical Observatory.	"	

APPENDIX H.

List of Lantern Slides Made during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

S. No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	REMARKS
1	Bagh.	Mahakal temple.	
2	"	Cave No. 2, before conservation.	
3	"	" " 2, after "	
4	"	" " 4, before "	
5	"	" " 4, after "	
6	"	" " 4, frame work on frescoes.	
7	"	" " 4, " " " another view.	
8	"	" " 5, before clearance.	
9	"	" " 4, fresco painting, elephant procession.	
10	"	" " 4, " " panel of ceiling.	
11	"	" " 4, " " a group of dancers.	
12	"	" " 4, " " a scene of sorrow.	
13	"	" " 4, " " elephant procession.	
14	Besnagar.	Khamb Baba.	
15	Chorpura.	An old Sivata temple.	
16	Gwalior Fort.	Jaina images.	
17	"	(Museum) Varaha (animal incarnation).	
18	Kulwar.	A memorial pillar.	
19	Narwar.	Jait Khamba.	
20	"	Fort, Hawapaur gate.	
21	"	" " " another.	
22	"	" Sikandar Lodi's Mosque.	
23	"	Kachheri Mahal, interior view.	
24	"	" " ornamental arch.	
25	"	" " " ceiling.	
26	Piparaghar.	Mahadev temple.	
27	Pohri.	Jal Mandir.	

APPENDIX H.—(contd.)

S. No.	Locality.	Object and Description.	REMARKS.
28	Rai.	Remains of a Jaina temple.	
29	Sesai.	A Jaina image.	
30	Agra.	Tomb of Itmad-ud-Daula.	
31	..	Moti Masjid.	
32	..	Taj Mahal.	
33	..	 interior view.	
34	..	Fort, interior of Moti Masjid.	
35	Ajanta.	Fresco painting in Caves, group of flying figures.	
36	..	Cave No. 19, exterior.	
37	..	A seated girl, back view.	
38	..	The capture of elephants.	
39	..	Cave No. 17, girl's head.	
40	..	King, queen and beggar.	
41	..	Cave No. 1, Figures from a wall painting.	
42	..	 a palace scene.	
43	..	 Prince Gautama and his wife Yasodhara with attendants.	
44	..	 A group of women in a boat.	
45	..	A <i>Yaksha</i> in the act of climbing up an elephant.	
46	Bhuvaneshvar.	Mukteshvar temple.	
47	Bijapur.	Tomb of Muhammad Adil Shah.	
48	..	Interior of the Jama Masjid.	
49	Chidambaram.	Siva temple tank with northern Gopura.	
50	Chittorgarh.	The Tower of Victory.	
51	Delhi (old).	Tomb of Humayun.	
52	Ellora.	Image of Indrani in the Jaina cave : Indra Sabha.	
53	..	Kailasa temple.	
54	..	Kailasa temple, secondary shrine.	

APPENDIX H.—(concl.)

S. No.	Locality	Object and Description.	REMARKS.
55	Ellora.	Kailasa temple, pedestal of the main temple.	
56	Gaya.	The Great Buddha temple.	
57	Madura.	Great temple, image of Subrahmanya in the hall of the thousand pillars.	
58	Mahabalipuram.	Rathas (rock-cut temples) and animal figures.	
59	Puri.	Jagannath temple.	
60	Rameshvaram.	Pillars of the temple.	
61	Sanchi.	East gateway, detail of carving.	
62	Taxia.	View of the Dharmarajika Stupa from north.	
63	Jaulian.	Stupa A/16 from south east.	
64	„	Sarasvati.	

Lists of Drawings Prepared during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

S. No.	Locality.	Description.	Scale.	REMARKS.
District Bhilsa.				
1	Basoda.	Site plan of Basoda Teonda Road proposed by the Archæological Department.	1" = 4'	Completed in ink.
2	Udaypur.	Plan of Udayesvar temple ..	"	"
3	"	Block plan of Udayesvar temple ..	1" = 16'	"
4	"	Detail of Vedi and an attendant shrine.	1" = 4'	"
District Esagarh.				
5	Chanderi.	Plan and elevations of proposed Johar monument at Johar Tal on Fort.	1" = 2'	In pencil.
6	"	Tracing of above	"	In ink.
7	"	Do.	"	"
8	"	Do.	"	"
District Gird.				
9	Gwalior.	Tracing of plan of Gujari Mahal ..	1" = 8'	
10	"	Sketch for the proposed <i>sikhara</i> of Chaturbhuj temple, Gwalior Fort.	"	
11	"	Tracing of above	"	
12	"	Tracing of the site plan of Maharani Jhansi's <i>Chhatri</i> .	1" = 12'	
Miscellaneous.				
13	..	Map of Gwalior State showing important places of Archæological interest.	1" = 32 miles	
14	..	Sketch of sunshade for the Archæological Office.	1" = 6'	
15	..	Map of India showing important places of Archæological interest.		
16	..	Index chart of Topo sheets for Gwalior State.	1" = 32 miles	Completed in ink.
17	..	Do. do. do. do.		

APPENDIX J.—(contd.)

S. No.	Name of Book.	REMARKS.
Chronology.		
21	Coins and Chronology of the Early Independent Sultans of Bengal by N. K. Bhattasali.	Purchased.
22	Chronology of Ancient India by S. N. Pradhan	..
Epigraphy.		
23	Kharoshthi Inscriptions, Part III, by E. J. Rapson	Gratis.
24	Epigraphia Indica, Vol. XVI, Part III	Purchased.
25	 IV	..
26	 XIX .. VII	Gratis.
27	 XX .. II	..
Ethnography.		
28	Anthropology, Vol. I, by Sir E. B. Taylor	Purchased.
29	 II	..
Guides.		
30	Mandu : the City of Joy by G. Yazdani	..
History.		
31	Pre-Musalman India, Vol. I, by V. Rangacharya	..
32	Hindu India from Original Sources, Part I, by S. K. Aiyangar	..
33	 Part II	..
34	A short history of Hindu India	..
35	The Aravindu Dynasty of Vijayanagar, Vol. I, by Dr. H. Heras.	..
36	The Pandyan Kingdom by Nilkantha Sastri	..
37	Studies in Gupta History by S. K. Aiyangar	..
38	आयंदेव कुल का इतिहास; क. दीवान प्रतिपालसिंह कृत	..
39	बुदेलखंड का इतिहास, भाग १ला	..
40	दक्षिणचरा मध्य युगीन इतिहासानी साधने, खंड १ला; म. ह. लारे कृत	..
Iconography.		
41	Die Figurable Plastik Der Guptazeit by Stella Kramrisch	Gratis.

APPENDIX J—(contd.)

S. No.	Name of Book.	REMARKS.
42	Iconography of Buddhist and Brahmanical Sculpture in the Dacca Museum by N. K. Bhattasali.	Purchased.
43	Portrait Sculpture in South India by T. G. Aravamuthan ..	"
44	Pala and Sena Sculptures by Stella Kramrisch	Gratis.
Journals and Periodicals.		
45-56	Modern Review from July 1930 to June 1931	Purchased.
57-58	Journal of the Mythic Society, Vol. XXI, Nos. 1 and 2 ..	"
59-70	Indian Antiquary from July 1930 to June 1931	Purchased.
71-73	Indian Historical Quarterly, Vol. VI, Nos. 2,3 & 4 ..	"
74	" " " " VII, No. 1	"
75-77	Journal of Indian History, Vol. IX, Parts 1,2, & 3 ..	Gratis.
78	Bharat Itihas Sanshodhak Mandal, Vol. X, No. 4	Purchased.
79-80	" " " " " XI, Nos. 1 and 2	"
81-83	Nagari Pracharini Patrika, Vol. XI, Nos. 1 to 3	"
84-85	Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, Vol. X, Parts 1-2 and 3-4.	"
86	" " " " " " Vol. XI, Part I	"
87	" " " " " " " XII " 1	"
88	The Journal of the Bihar and Orissa Research Society, Vol. XVII, Part I, 1931.	"
89	Index to Indian Antiquary, Vol. LIX, 1930	"
90	Journal of the Andhra Historical Research Society, Vol. IV, Parts 3 and 4.	"
91-93	" " " " " Vol. V., Nos. 1 to 3 ..	"
Literature.		
94	History of Dharmasastra, Vol. I, by P. V. Kane	"
95	Subhashitavali by Vallabhadeva	"
96	History of Sanskrit Literature: Vedic Period by C. V. Vaidya ..	"
97	Indian Cultural Influence in Cambodia by B. R. Chatterji ..	"
98	Krishna Problem by S. N. Tadpatrikar	"

APPENDIX J—(contd.)

S. No.	Name of Book.	REMARKS.
99	The Shah Namah of Firdausi described by J. V. S. Wilkinson ..	Purchased.
100	Mahabharat Adiparva Fascicule 5 by V. S. Sukhatankar ..	..
101	Sulabha Vastu Sastra by R. S. Deshpande ..	..
Miscellaneous.		
102	Madhav Gita, Vol. I, by B. R. Bhagwat ..	..
103	Old Civilization of the New World by A. N. Verrill ..	..
104	Land Marks of the Deccan by S. A. Asgar Bilgrami Asafjahi ..	..
105	General Statutory Rules: Government of India, Vol. III, 1926, Legislative Department.	..
106	Proceedings of the 12th Session of Indian Historical Records Commission, Vol. XII, December 1929.	Gratis.
107	Proceedings of the 5th Indian Oriental Conference, Vol. I ..	..
108	" " " " " " " " II ..	..
Museum.		
109-111	Bulletin of the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, Nos. 170, 171 & 173	..
112	Bulletin of the Madras Government Museum (the Adichanallur Skulls by S. Zuckerman, M. A.)	..
113	Do. (Supplement to the Littoral Fauna of Krusadia Island in the Gulf of Minner by various authors).	..
114	Do. (The Scyphomedusal of Madras and the neighbouring coast of M. G. K. Menon).	..
Photography.		
115	List of Archæological Photo Negatives of the North-West Frontier Province, Baluchistan, Kashmir and the Punjab (Mahomedan and British Monuments) stored in the Office of the Superintendent, Archæological Survey, Frontier Circle, Lahore, March 1930.	..
Pre-History.		
116	Pre-Historic India by P. Mitra ..	Purchased.
Religion.		
117	Early History of Vaishnavism in South India by S. K. Aiyangar.	..
118	Comparative Religion by A. A. Macdonell ..	..

APPENDIX J.—(concl'd).

S. No.	Name of Book.	REMARKS.
119	A History of Indian Literature, Vol. I, by M. Winternitz ..	Purchased.
State Publications.		
120	Administration of the Gwalior State during the Year 1927-28 ..	Gratis.
121	Hand-Book of Department of Records	..
122	General Statistics of the Gwalior State for Samvat 1979 ..	..
123	Correspondence Manual, Gwalior State	Purchased.
124	संन्युअल खिताबात व एजाजहा, सम्बत १९६७	..
125	कानून मोटर गाडियान, रियासत ग्वालियर, सम्बत १९७९	..
126	मजमूआ जाब्ता फौजदारी, रियासत ग्वालियर, सम्बत १९५३	..
127	मजमूआ ताजीरात ग्वालियर, सम्बत १९८२	..
128	रियासत ग्वालियर की परस्तिशगाह और मजहबी ओकाफ को इम्दाव और निगरानी का कानून, सम्बत १९८३	Gratis.
129	कदीम इमारती धावगार व कदीम अशियाय की हिफाजत का कानून, रियासत ग्वालियर, सम्बत १९८६	Purchased.

List of Expenditure Incurred during the Year 1930-31, Samvat 1987.

S.No.	Head.	Amount current year.			Amount last year.			TOTAL.	REMARKS.
		Rs.	a.	p.	Rs.	a.	p.		
1	Salaries	12,766	5	2	..	..	..		
2	T. A.	2,250	2	6	1	8	3		
3	Contingencies	1,415	9	3	..	..	..		
4	Books	397	8	8	..	..	..		
5	Miscellaneous	396	0	0	..	..	..		
6	Publication	993	0	0	1	15	6		
7	General Saving, current year	43	13	0	..	..	..		
8	Museum (Collection & Upkeep)	1,262	12	0	..	..	..		
9	Works (Conservation Proper)	11,544	11	4	113	13	8		
	(a) Recurring Grant	Rs.	3,524	15	9	..	..		
	(b) Non-recurring Grant	Rs.	7,230	2	10	..	..		
		Rs.	10,755	2	7	..	..		
	Annual Up-keep of Monuments already conserved.	Rs.	639	10	3	..	..		
	Miscellaneous.								
	(a) Current year	Rs.	149	14	6	..	..		
	(b) Last year	..	113	13	8	..	..		
			263	12	2	..	..		
		Total Rs.	11,658	9	0	..	..		
10	Expenditure over and above Budget Grant	..	113	15	6	..	..		
		Total	31,183	13	5	117	5	5	
			31,301	2	10	..	..		

APPENDIX L.

Statement of Income Realized during Samvat 1987, Year 1930-31.

S. No.	Item.	Amount.	REMARKS.
1	By Sale of Books ..	Rs. a. p. 117 6 8	
2	" " " Tender Forms ..	8 0 0	
3	" " " Photographs ..	107 2 6	
4	Miscellaneous ..	20 0 0	
	Total ..	252 9 2	

(a) Cave No. 4 at Bagh : Frieze after repair with new supports.

(b) Cave No. 4 at Bagh : Two new pillars.

(a) An old brick temple at Kherat, before conservation.

(b) An old brick temple at Kherat, after conservation.

(a) An old brick temple at Kherat: Images in open air.

(b) Khan Daura Khan's tomb at Gwalior (near view from south).

(a) An old brick temple at Kherat: An image of Siva and Parvati.

(b) A copper image of a goddess (in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(c) A brass image of a god (in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(a) An old gun from Narwar (now placed near the Jaivilas Palace at Lashkar).

(b) An old gun from Bhilsa (now placed near the Jaivilas Palace at Lashkar).

(a) Memorial of Mahadji Scindia at Lashkar (general view).

(b) Excavations at Pawaya : A fragment of lintel of a gateway (general view).

(a) Excavations at Pawaya : Trivikrama on a fragment of lintel.

(b) Excavations at Pawaya : Bali's sacrifice on a fragment of lintel.

(a) Excavations at Pawaya : A scene of music and dance on a fragment of lintel.

(b) An old memorial pillar at Sesai.

(a) Krishna playing flute (a painting in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(b) A loving reception of a victorious warrior by his beloved (a painting in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(c) A Muhammadan chief riding on an elephant (a painting in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

(d) A princess playing on a guitar (a painting in the Arch. Museum at Gwalior).

Central Archaeological Library,
NEW DELHI. 27325.

Call No. 913 041/trace/D.A.

Author— 1930-31.

Title— Annual Report of Arch. Dept.
Gwalior State

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